

Data Completion Guide

Daily Q Form

Daily Q Assessment Completed everyday for the inpatient ICU stay. Data reflects events for the previous 24 hrs: 0000-2400.		
Date*	Date	Record the date for which the form has been filled
Care of the ventilated patients		
Variable name	Data entry format	Definition for collection
Ventilation P*	Dropdown list	Self vent: No breaths are delivered by a mechanical device for a period of one hour during the day. Mechanical vent: All or some of the breaths or a portion of the breaths (pressure support) are delivered by a mechanical device for one hour during the day. Please record the highest ventilation support in the last 24hrs
Route of ventilation*	Dropdown list	If 'Ventilation' is 'Mechanical vent': options are The type of mechanically assisted breathing during the first hour of admission. If multiple modes are used, please report the most invasive. ETT Tracheostomy NIV Mask Please record the highest ventilation support in the last 24hrs
HFNC^	Options: Yes, No	If 'Ventilation' is 'Self-vent': High-flow oxygen delivered via a specialized device, with FiO ₂ > 0.4 and at a flow rate of at least 30 L/min
Spontaneous breathing trial (SBT)	Options: Yes, No	If 'Ventilation' is 'Mechanical vent': and 'Route of ventilation' is 'Tracheostomy': or 'ETT': A trial of spontaneous breathing, defined as one of the following four; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trial of 'T' piece - Pressure support with low support (PS of 5-8) - CPAP (i.e. only PEEP between 0-5) - Automatic tube compensation with CPAP - Not eligible for SBT

Lowest FiO2	% or number ≤1.0	<i>If 'Ventilation' is 'Mechanical vent':</i> Lowest inspired oxygen concentration delivered for a minimum of one hour.
Lowest PEEP	mmH2O	<i>If 'Ventilation' is 'Mechanical vent':</i> Lowest positive end expiratory pressure for a minimum of one hour.
SpO2	%	The lowest arterial oxygen saturation measured by pulse oximetry.
Respiratory rate highest	b/min	The highest respiratory rate recorded.
Chest X-ray	Options: Yes, No	Was a chest X-ray performed today?
Chest X-ray infiltrates	Options: Yes, No	<i>If 'Chest X-ray' is 'Yes':</i> Record if infiltrates were found on CXR
Venous thromboembolism (VTE) prophylaxis	Dropdown list	<i>If 'Ventilation' is 'Mechanical vent':</i> Use of mechanical or pharmacological prophylaxis in the prevention of venous thromboembolism.
Contraindication	Dropdown list	<i>If 'VTE prophylaxis' is 'None':</i> A contraindication preventing the use of mechanical and pharmacological prophylaxis.
Stress ulcer prophylaxis	Options: Yes, No	<i>If 'Ventilation' is 'Mechanical vent':</i> A drug is prescribed for the purpose of stress ulcer prophylaxis
Drug	Dropdown list	<i>If 'Stress ulcer prophylaxis' is 'Yes':</i> The named drug from the provided list used for stress ulcer prophylaxis.
Inadvertent/Accidental extubation	Options: Yes, No	<i>If 'Ventilation' is 'Mechanical vent':</i> The unexpected or unplanned extubation of a patient.
Head of Bed >30° or patient sat up (if no degree measure)	Options: Yes, No	<i>If 'Ventilation' is 'Mechanical vent':</i> <i>Position of the head of bed</i> Please record HoB position daily based on observed elevation at time of review. If no degree measure patients have hip flexion with chest and head elevated using pillows or have total bed tilt (Trendelenburg) .
CVS care		
<i>Variable name</i>	<i>Data entry format</i>	<i>Definition for collection</i>
Highest temperature	°F or °C	Highest recorded temperature.
Cardiovascular support	Options: Yes, No	Use of continuous intravenous vasoactive medication for a minimum period of one hour.

Vasoactive drugs increased	Options: Yes, No	<i>If 'Cardiovascular support' is 'Yes':</i> An increase in the use of vasoactive medication (either number of agents or dosage of an agent) for a minimum period of one hour.
Central venous catheter	Options: New, Insitu, No	The presence of a central venous catheter
Site	Dropdown list	<i>If 'Central venous catheter' is 'New' or 'In situ':</i> Select the location of the new or existing central venous catheter
Renal care		
<i>Variable name</i>	<i>Data entry format</i>	<i>Definition for collection</i>
Urinary catheter	Options: New, Insitu, No	The presence of a urinary catheter
Haemodialysis catheter	Options: New, Insitu, No	The presence of a haemodialysis catheter
Site	Dropdown list	<i>If 'Haemodialysis catheter' or ' is 'New' or 'In situ':</i> Select the location of the new or existing haemodialysis catheter
Renal replacement therapy	Options: Yes, No	Use of renal replacement therapy. Any duration of renal replacement therapy is considered as 'Yes'.
Type of the therapy	Dropdown list	<i>If 'Renal replacement therapy' is 'Yes':</i> The type of renal replacement therapy used.
Neuro care		
<i>Variable name</i>	<i>Data entry format</i>	<i>Definition for collection</i>
Sedated	Options: Yes, No	Use of sedative drugs for a minimum of one hour. If bolus sedation, then 2 or more bolus.
Spontaneous Awakening Trial or (sedation hold).	Options: Yes, No	<i>If 'Sedated' is 'Yes':</i> Spontaneous awakening trial (SAT or "sedation hold") a period during which sedating medications that are being used to treat the patient were held in order to determine whether the patient requires ongoing sedation or can be managed without sedatives.
Target RASS	Dropdown list	<i>If 'Ventilation' is 'Mechanical vent' and 'Sedated' =Yes</i> The target RASS is a measure of sedation, awakesness and agitation. The target RASS is the target set each day on the ward round.

		The options are available as a drop down. <i>+4 to -5 and 'No target set'</i>
Actual RASS score	Dropdown list	<i>If 'Ventilation' is 'Mechanical vent' and 'Sedated' =Yes</i> The RASS is a measure of sedation, awakesness and agitation. The actual RASS is the measured (observed) `RASS either immediately prior to a SAT or at 0800. The options are available as a drop down. <i>+4 to -5 and 'Not recorded'</i>
Infection Management		
<i>Variable name</i>	<i>Data entry format</i>	<i>Definition for collection</i>
Highest white cell count	x10 ⁹ /L or x10 ³ /mm ³ or x10 ³ /μL	The highest recorded serum white blood cell count.
Lowest white cell count	x10 ⁹ /L or x10 ³ /mm ³ or x10 ³ /μL	The lowest recorded serum white blood cell count.
Infection	Dropdown list	Presence of a confirmed or suspected infection. Select 'None' if no infection was reported.
Source	Dropdown list	<i>If 'Infection' is 'Suspected' OR 'Confirmed':</i> The source of infection from a list of body systems.
Antimicrobial use daily	Options: Yes, No	Use of antimicrobial therapy. Even if only one dose has been administered, this is 'Yes' Denominator- all ICU patients Eligibility = all.
Antimicrobial type	Dropdown list	<i>If 'Antimicrobial use daily' is 'yes':</i> The type of antimicrobial from a drug list.
Microbiology		
<i>Variable name</i>	<i>Data entry format</i>	<i>Definition for collection</i>
Culture obtained today	Options: Yes, No	Was a culture sample taken today.
Type of culture	Dropdown list	Type of culture. <i>1, Blood 2, Urine 3, CSF 4, Stool 5, Sputum 6, BAL 7, Wound</i>
Culture report	Dropdown list	<i>1, Growth 2, No growth 3, Pending 4, None Obtained 5, None Pending</i>

		<p>Record whether a new culture report was available today.</p> <p>Growth: if a new culture report was available today and growth was identified.</p> <p>No growth: if a new culture report was available today and no growth was identified.</p> <p>Pending: if a culture report was obtained and results are pending</p> <p>None obtained: if no cultures have been obtained during the patient's stay</p> <p>None pending: if results of all cultures taken are available and have been previously entered on the patient's record.</p>
Date culture taken	yyyy-mm-dd	<i>If 'Culture report' is 'Growth' or 'No growth':</i> Record the date the specimen was taken.
Organism	Dropdown list	<i>If 'Culture report' is 'Growth':</i> Organism list referred by HELICS (Note: refer Organism list sheet)
Resistance name	Dropdown list	<i>If 'Organism' is recorded:</i> From the dropdown list, record the antimicrobial resistance for the organism
Sensitivity name	Dropdown list	<i>If 'Organism' is recorded:</i> From the dropdown list, record the antimicrobial sensitivity for the organism
Colony forming units (CFU)	Numerical units (per ml)	Record the colony forming units
Skin care		
<i>Variable name</i>	<i>Data entry format</i>	<i>Definition for collection</i>
Pressure sore	Options: Yes, No	New pressure/ compression related injury to skin (New meaning which occurred within the ICU)
Site of pressure sore	Dropdown list	<i>If 'Pressure Injury' is 'Yes':</i> -Back of the head -Ears, face, mouth -Shoulders -Elbows -Lower back -Buttocks/ sacrum -Hips -Inner knees -Heels -Other

Grade	Dropdown list	If 'Pressure Injury' is 'Yes': 1,2,3,4,5
Mobilisation and rehabilitation		
<i>Variable name</i>	<i>Data entry format</i>	<i>Definition for collection</i>
Physiotherapy/Mobilisation	Dropdown list	<p>If 'Ventilation' is 'Mechanical vent':</p> <p>Patients ventilated may receive passive or active physiotherapy in the ICU. The type of physiotherapy provided should be recorded daily. The event may occur at any time in the previous 24 hours. Some patients may not be eligible for daily physio (for example due to cardiovascular instability, or because they are at the end of life or because they are receiving a procedure).</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. On bed physiotherapy 2. Out of bed mobilisation 3. No physiotherapy delivered 4. No physiotherapy delivered due to patient not eligible

Definitions for calculation of HAIs		
HAI	Reference	Definition
CAUTI	CDC-NHSI 2019	<p>Defined once per patient.</p> <p>Denominator is patients who had urinary catheter at any time (catheter is either 'new' or 'insitu').</p> <p>Numerator: Can happen on the day the urinary catheter was 'insitu' and on all days after it.</p> <p>Positive urine culture: Pathogen cultured (daily Q ("culture report" = "growth" or positive_culture == "Yes") + "Type of culture"= "Urine") AND Fever (temperature >38°C)</p>
CLABSI	CDC-NHSI 2019	Defined once per patient.

		<p>From daily Q form.</p> <p>Numerator: Positive blood culture: (daily Q ("culture report" = "growth" or positive_culture == "Yes") and "Type of culture"= "Blood").</p> <p>AND Fever (temperature > 38 °C), OR hypotension (cardiovascular support= Yes).</p> <p>Denominator: CVC 'Yes' or 'Insitu' for 2 or more consecutive days, at most 48 hours before date of fever AND date of positive culture.</p>
<p>IVAC</p>	<p>Infection-related Ventilator-Associated Complication (IVAC) by CDC-NHSN.</p>	<p>Denominator : Eligible if mechanically ventilated for at least 2 consecutive daily forms.</p> <p>Ventilation needs to have happened before:</p> <p>Numerator: A new antimicrobial agent(s) is started (*please note we are not using the full criteria for antimicrobials as per the CDC guideline)</p> <p>AND 1. Temperature > 38 °C or < 36°C, OR 2. white blood cell count ≥ 12,000 cells/mm3 or ≤ 4,000 cells/mm3.</p> <p>AND 1. Increase in daily minimum FiO2 of ≥0.20 (20 points) over the previous 24 hr reported value OR 2. Increase in daily minimum PEEP values of ≥3 cmH2O over the previous 24 hr period reported value.</p> <p>*New antimicrobial agent commencement defined as: `DailyAssessment.antibiotics == "Yes"` and it's the first date a new name has appeared in one of the `DailyAssessment.name_of_the_antibiotic` variables.</p>

Definitions for calculation of quality indicators		
Indicator	Reference	Definition
Daily Venous Thrombotic Event (VTE) prophylaxis	doi:10.1097/CCM.00000000000003155	Expressed as a percentage, either calculated per patient or per day. Numerator: Number of eligible patients that receive VTE prophylaxis on a day they were eligible for prophylaxis. Denominator: the total number of ventilated patients in the ICU eligible to receive mechanical or pharmacological VTE prophylaxis. Eligible: mechanically ventilated, with no contra-indications to VTE prophylaxis.
Duration of mechanical ventilation/ ventilator free days.	doi:10.1513/AnnalsATS.201610-792OC. PMID: 28033033.	Number of days on mechanical ventilation in ICU, or days liberated prior to ICU discharge
Ventilator free days	doi:10.1097/00003246-200208000-00016	The number of days between successful weaning from mechanical ventilation (i.e. extubation day) until hospital discharge.
Stress ulcer prophylaxis	doi:10.1097/CCM.0000000000000334	Percentage calculated either per patient or per day. Numerator: Number of patients receiving stress ulcer prophylaxis on any day of ventilation. Denominator: Patients mechanically ventilated for at least one day.
Re-intubation rate	doi:10.1097/CCM.00000000000002327	Percentage calculated per patient. Denominator: Extubated patients defined as having either ETT or tracheostomy at any time during ICU stay, then having it removed. Numerator: Reintubation within 24 hours of extubation. Defined as ETT or tracheostomy going back in on the next day.
Daily Spontaneous Awakening Trials (SAT)	doi:10.1056/NEJM199612193352502	Percentage per patient: Denominator: patients mechanically ventilated and sedated ≥ 1 day Numerator: patients receiving SAT on any day they're ventilated and sedated.
Duration (days) of empirical antibiotic use in the ICU	https://dx.doi.org/10.1007%2Fs40506-014-0015-3	Number of days the patient received antibiotics during ICU admission
Post ICU Quality of Life and mortality 30 days post ICU	doi:10.1037/pne0000170	Measured at 90-day post-discharge follow up call. The SF-36 was used to assess health-related QOL. For each variable item, scores are coded, summed, and transformed on a scale from 0 (worst possible health state measured by the questionnaire) to 100 (best possible health state). Within each domain, a score of <50 = "low value of QOL" and >50 "high".
Richmond Agitation and	doi: 10.1055/s-2001-13834	Measure daily RASS score for ICU patients mechanically ventilated

Sedation Scale		<p>for 24 hours or more. Compare the measured RASS scores with the target RASS score set for the day.</p> <p>Percentage of ICU patients mechanically ventilated for 24 hours or more who achieved the target RASS score . Numerator: ICU patients mechanically ventilated for 24 hours or more who achieved the target RASS score. Denominator: All ICU patients mechanically ventilated for 24 hours or more</p>
Incidence of VTE	<p>doi:10.1056/NEJMoa2103417</p>	<p>Incidence of VTE defined as follows:</p> <p>Proximal deep vein thrombosis is a thrombus located in the axillary vein or more proximal, including the internal jugular vein, and a thrombus located in the popliteal vein or more proximal. Confirmation requires imaging with techniques that include ultrasound or CT scan. Confirmed pulmonary embolus: Segmental or multi-sub-segmental pulmonary emboli that is confirmed using CT pulmonary angiography</p> <p>Numerator: Number of patients who develop VTE. Denominator: All ICU patients ventilated 24 hours or more</p>
Length of ICU stay	<p>doi:10.1097/01.CCM.0000240233.01711.D9</p>	<p>Calculated in days. Number of days between admission and discharge. The day of admission is counted as day 1.</p>
Incidence of pressure injury	<p>doi:10.1097/01.ASW.0000269314.23015.e9</p>	<p>Percentage calculated per patient.</p> <p>Numerator: Patients with pressure sore recorded at any time during ICU stay.</p> <p>Denominator: Patients mechanically ventilated at any time during ICU stay.</p>